

Epigraphic Pāli as a Southeast Asian Geographic Zone

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Abstract

This essay is about the geography of a language. It is about the relation of Pāli to the land and to the historical map. Pāli is the scriptural and liturgical language of the Theravaṃsa, a Buddhist monastic tradition that originated in India but since the early centuries BCE has been historically centred in Sri Lanka. Its long-lasting descendant is the Theravāda of the Great Monastery of the old capital, Anuradhapura. The article focusses on the Pāli epigraphic record. It finds that there are no early Pāli inscriptions anywhere in South Asia and that the earliest and most extensive Pāli epigraphic corpus is not from Sri Lanka but from mainland Southeast Asia, where extracts from canonical texts were inscribed in the second half of the first millennium CE.

This essay is about the geography of a language. It is about the relation of Pāli to the land and to the historical map. It looks at a time period from the time of the Buddha up to the end of the first millennium CE, that is, a *longue durée* of one thousand five hundred years of Buddhist history, constituted by about five hundred years of orality followed by one thousand years during which oral and written cultures interacted. This was by no means a static period: monastics were on the move across Asia and monastic Buddhism participated in dynamic networks of social, intellectual, and material exchange. It was a period of intrareligious cooperation and confrontation, of conflict and contradiction, as Buddhism advanced and retreated in fits and starts. The age was famously memorialized by the peripatetic Chinese pilgrim-scholars Faxian, Yijing, and Xuanzang. Monastic institutions were contracting in some parts of the subcontinent and expanding in others, both within and outside of India. Ideas and ideals circulated across networks that connected widely dispersed Buddhist centres; canons, canonical languages, and canonical practices evolved while philosophy, iconography, and art saw rapid and innovative developments. But time took its toll and the Buddhist monastic system proved to be unsustainable as systems of patronage

changed and the social and religious environment became increasingly more competitive and inhospitable. The system went into decline and slowly broke down. Libraries were destroyed or abandoned and centuries of history and intellectual endeavour turned into dust and were lost forever. Today Buddhism's long and complex trajectory can only be traced through the patient study of patchworks of fragmented epigraphs and vandalized material remains. To make sense of all this we need to read the material landscape in tandem with the literary monuments of monastic metaphysics.

The formation of Buddhist canons was a great multilingual project. Throughout the period, classical canons were continually formulated and reformulated as the different schools tried to preserve and transmit the Buddha's teaching together with their own textual legacies. Some of the old oral canons were transferred to writing but many were lost as reciters passed away and archaic schools died out or were absorbed by other schools.¹ Scriptural languages migrated and translated canons were formed—in Chinese in the East Asian sphere, in Tibetan in the Tibetan and Himalayan regions, and in Central Asian languages across Central Asia. Manuscript canons were copied and recopied, revised and copied again. The Buddha's word did not stand still but received continual editorial attention in the attempt to preserve it to perfection. By the fifth century, Vasubandhu and other Tripiṭaka masters recognized that the 'root recitations' that were collected after the Buddha's demise were lost, and accepted the fact that the corpus of the Buddha's teachings, the *Buddhavacana*, was only incompletely and imperfectly preserved.

Mapping Pāli might seem simple but is in fact complicated and even contentious. This is because Pāli is 'homeless' insofar as its place of origin or historical homeland is not known. No one has been able to identify an ancient 'Pāli-land' once populated by 'Pāli-speakers'. For this there may be good reason, since the evidence suggests that rather than a displaced 'natural' language, Pāli is an artificial and hybrid literary language. As long ago as the third century BCE, a branch of the Theravāṃsa migrated to Ceylon with a corpus of scriptures and exegetical traditions and went on to establish this recension of Gotama the Buddha's teachings on the island.

The premise of this essay is that Pāli inscriptions have been found only in Southeast Asia, in a geographical area that I call the 'Pāli epigraphic zone'.² This zone spreads across the region that in antiquity was known

as Suvāṇṇabhūmi,³ the Land of Gold, and that we now know as mainland Southeast Asia.⁴ The zone embraces two main subregions. One is the Irrawaddy River valley and delta in lower Burma: I call this the ‘western region’. The other spreads from the Chao Phraya River valley in lower Siam to the Korat plateau and to eastern Siam and central Cambodia. I call this subregion the Central Mainland Southeast Asian region. These names and distinctions are provisional conventions of my own devising.

As a linguistic zone, as a zone of language reference and use, the Pāli epigraphic zone is a physically non-continuous series or chain of historical core areas that interpenetrate the wide region across both time and space. This broad band and its subregions are not natural or unitary linguistic regions.⁵ Nor are they discrete ecological, economic, or political zones, although they overlap with these categories inasmuch as they are, like any other region, historically and culturally determined. The degree of overlap with antique states or polities—such as Śrīkṣetra, Dvāravatī, or Canāśa—is an intriguing question but beyond the scope of this essay, and, at any rate, the extent and boundaries of these entities are far from clear.⁶ As an epigraphic zone, the regions are bounded by time, but the dating of the records is uncertain, and the only access we have to the earliest periods is through the material record. Not a single middle Pāli record bears a date. There is, however, temporal continuity in the sense that the zone remains active today. As a living religious language, Pāli is published in print and electronic media, studied in monasteries and universities, and recited daily by hundreds of thousands if not millions of people. The Pāli epigraphic zone attests to the continuing use of Pāli for about one thousand five hundred years. For this reason, Pāli occupies a special place in the historical and modern consciousness of lived Buddhism.

Pāli is a Middle Indo-Aryan dialect or variety of early Prakrit, but the Pāli epigraphic zone is not located within areas where Indic or Indian languages were spoken in the past or are spoken today. That is, there is a disjuncture between the written records of Pāli and the languages of the ‘host’ populations. In the western subregion, Pāli inscriptions are associated with records in Pyu or Tircul, an extinct Tibeto-Burman language,⁷ and, somewhat later, with the Mon-Khmer languages Old and Middle Mon and the Tibeto-Burman language Burmese.⁸ In Southeast Asia, Pāli is written in specific scripts that are adapted from Southern Brāhmī (a conventional name for the form of the early Brāhmī script that developed in South India) and evolved into the writing systems of the vernacular languages.⁹ In the eastern subregion, Pāli inscriptions cohabit with records in Old Mon, and, somewhat later, with Old Khmer

and with Thai and other members of the Tai-Kadai family. According to current understandings, Mon, Khmer, and Vietnamese are the primary languages of the Austroasiatic language group.¹⁰ The writing systems of the first two belong to the greater Indic script family that is built around the developed science of phonetics that had developed orally before the Buddha's time and that defined the structure of later alphabets used by classical languages of Pāli and Sanskrit. Uniquely among Austroasiatic languages, Vietnamese was originally written in Chinese characters.

The large Austroasiatic language family is dispersed across northern India, Bangladesh, and Nepal and the southern borderlands of China. Only two members of the family, Vietnamese and Khmer, have official status as modern national languages. Some Mon-Khmer languages have official status in Indian states, for example Khasi in Meghalaya and Santali and Mundari in Jharkhand.¹¹ In Burma, the Wa language (Palaungic) is widely used in Wa State bordering the Chinese province of Yunnan. The other Austroasiatic languages are spoken by numerically small communities scattered across the map of South Asia (India, Bangladesh, and Nepal) and of Southeast Asia, intersected by areas where other languages are used. Today they survive in pockets, enclaves, and corridors across a map furrowed by varying ecological and altitudinal landscapes and have no 'official' or 'state' status. The Austroasiatic languages are likely to be Southeast Asia's autochthonous languages, interspersed with other language families brought by later migrations. On the evidence of DNA, the Indian members appear to have migrated from Southeast Asia, but the details are far from clear.¹² Theories of language migration are difficult to substantiate and are socially and politically contested.

During this period, there are no original Pāli compositions—all of the middle Pāli inscriptions are excerpts of texts, or what I call 'citation inscriptions'. These include numerous examples of the *ye dhammā* stanza, plus versions of the formulas of conditioned arising and the four realities realized by the noble ones, as well as key verses that summarize Gotama Buddha's teachings.¹³ Throughout the zone, a similar script, or similar scripts, are used. These are Indic writing systems derived on the whole from Southern Brāhmī. The scripts are written in both formal/calligraphic and cursive styles; they are used consistently and are generally punctuated correctly. Sanskrit inscriptions in similar scripts are found throughout the zone, but these are donative or royal records rather than Buddhist texts. There are also early vernacular records: in the western region in Pyu and in the eastern region in Old Mon and Old Khmer.

The Pāli epigraphic zone covers much of western and central Southeast Asia. Are there any other epigraphic zones in this extremely diverse linguistic region of Southeast Asia? Citation inscriptions are few in Cambodia and Champa (middle coastal Vietnam), perhaps because Buddhism did not develop strongly in these regions or perhaps because the epigraphic customs of the local Buddhist communities were different—or a combination of these and other factors. There are, however, a very few Buddhist citation inscriptions in Prakrit and Sanskrit in the Mekong river delta, that is, in Cambodia and southern Vietnam. Sanskrit is also the language of scriptures cited in the central and southern Thai-Malay peninsula and the ‘islands of the Southern Sea’, that is, in Malaysia, Brunei, and Indonesia, an area where to date no Pāli inscriptions have been noted. The language of citation inscription depends on the classical or canonical languages adopted by regional Buddhist communities. This subject is inadequately understood and existing studies tend to be unconvincing as they are dependent on outdated and inaccurate notions of ‘Hīnayāna’, ‘Mahāyāna’, and ‘Tantra’. Modern linguistic studies rarely examine the role of canonical languages or their interaction with regional languages, an odd situation which strikes me as markedly unsatisfactory.¹⁴ It does not seem possible to accurately understand the deep evolution of Southeast Asian alphabets or languages without recognizing the pervasive influence of their Indic language source materials, in the same way that etymological dictionaries of English record not only Latin or Germanic, etc., origins but also Indo-European roots.

Cross-regional script use and epigraphic choices like the *ye dharmā* and *ajñānāc-cīyate* stanzas point to an earlier map of broad cultural interactions connected by maritime routes linking Kedah to Borneo to Java.¹⁵ Excerpts from Mahāyāna texts are found in Kedah and Sumatra, and *dhāraṇīs* (spells/incantations) in insular Southeast Asia, the Mekong delta, and Ceylon.¹⁶ In the colonial and post-colonial periods, shifting political powers reconfigured what were once organic contiguous and interactive cultural conglomerations. The result has been that modern nations and their borders mask the connectivities of ancient cultural federations.

In sum, beyond the Pāli zone, the rest of mainland Southeast Asia is a mixed zone, with Prakrit and Sanskrit citations, and the Thai-Malay peninsula and the islands of Nusantara belong to what we may call a ‘Sanskritic epigraphic zone.’¹⁷ Admittedly and inevitably, the delineation

of these zones is based on fragmentary and incomplete records: that is, the inscriptions that have been recovered, preserved, and published to date. Many others may await discovery, may have gone into private collections, or may have been melted down to recycle the metal and hence lost forever. Some may still be enshrined deep within stūpas as had been originally intended.

In order to clarify the nature of this *Southeast* Asian Pāli epigraphic zone, let us take a broad look at related aspects of language and epigraphy in *South* Asia. It may seem surprising that there are no Pāli inscriptions, whether early or middle, in South Asia, whether in the mainland or in Sri Lanka.¹⁸ Suppose that later archaeologists had access to the South and Southeast Asian epigraphic record up to only the year CE 1000, they would likely conclude that Pāli was known and used only in Southeast Asia, and that Southeast Asia—perhaps the polities of Dvāravatī or Śrīkṣetra—was the home of the Pāli language. They would not dream that Pāli had any connection with India or Lanka.

What, then, about Sri Lanka—Sīhaladīpa, Tambapaṇṇī, Laṅkādīpa—where the Pāli language has been preserved and cultivated, and has been used for liturgy, devotional practice, and scholarship for over two millennia? Where, according to the chronicles or *vaṃsas*, the Pāli scriptures were first written down in the first century BCE? Whether or not the latter is the case, on the whole island of Lanka there are no ancient or middle Pāli inscriptions, and in comparison to those of Sukhothai and Ayuthaya in Thailand, there are not many later Pāli inscriptions (that is, from the eleventh century on). How can we explain this silence? Or do we need to explain it—is there any reason to expect Lanka and Southeast Asia to have shared the same epigraphic practices through the centuries? An interesting anomaly is that Lanka did share one epigraphic practice with South and Southeast Asia—that of installing inscribed texts to empower monuments. But none of these installation texts are in Pāli and none of them are Theravādin: they include a golden Perfection of Wisdom (*Prajñāparamitā*), the Kāśyapa Chapter (*Kāśyapa-parivarta*) or *Ratnakūṭa*, and some *dharanī* or incantation texts—all in Sanskrit (some in a north Indian script), and all related to Mahāyāna thought, liturgy, and practice.

Epigraphy and iconography demonstrate that different strands of Buddhist thought and practice flourished on the island through the first millennium and that Mahāyāna was prominent among them. Literary confirmation of this state of affairs comes from the Pāli chronicles

and commentaries themselves, which, despite their mission to present a single narrative of Theravaṃsa triumphalism, attest to a continual struggle against the complex of Vaitulya/Vaidalya/Vaipulya (Pāli *vetulla*, *vedalla*, *vepulla*) ideas and practices.¹⁹ Literary witnesses to the interchanges and conflicts between Mahāyānist thought and practice and the institutional Theravāda include the *Laṅkāvatāra-sūtra* with its majestic introduction set in the sea around Lanka and featuring the demon king Rāvaṇa. Multiple Chinese sources also attest unequivocally to the significant status of Mahāyāna and Tantra on the island throughout the centuries. This may in part explain why, as an epigraphic zone of Buddhist language, Lanka is a Sanskrit zone.²⁰

Early South Asia is on the whole a zone of Prakrit inscriptions.²¹ The inscriptions were mediated not only by the Buddhist *saṃghas* but also by brahmins and the court. Sanskrit had not yet been elevated to the role of *the* prestige language: the early Prakritic inscriptions number in the thousands, and new records continue to be found.²² They include inscriptions painted on rock surfaces and cave walls in addition to those engraved on boulders and pillars. There are so many and the published literature is so dispersed in periodicals, series, reports, and independent volumes, all in various modern Indian and European languages, that it is not easy—and even, perhaps, impossible—to keep track of the current state of knowledge.²³ Newly discovered donative inscriptions from Satdhara near Sanchi, from Sanchi itself, from Ujjain, from the recently excavated stūpas at Deorkothar (Madhya Pradesh),²⁴ Phanigiri (Telangana),²⁵ and Kanaganahalli (Karnataka)²⁶—all of these need to be added to the record and integrated into the study of the history of Buddhism in South Asia.

One type of epigraph that is important for the study of Buddhist texts, history, and literature is the ‘label inscription’. These are not citations as such but rather short labels or captions which identify a narrative scene or character; that is, they draw on early and otherwise lost canons and canonical lore. The best known and perhaps the earliest are those from the Bharhut stūpa in eastern Madhya Pradesh, dating to the second to first centuries BCE. There are occasional examples from other sites like Pauni in Maharashtra, and the corpus of label inscriptions has recently been considerably augmented by those from the great stūpa at Kanaganahalli.²⁷ The label inscriptions are generally ‘open to the eye’, that is, they are positioned where they can be easily seen or read, and they are frequently associated with donative or other records. The labels are all in Prakrit—none are in Pāli properly speaking.

The fact that there is no epigraphic evidence for Pāli in Lanka raises the question of where the language *was* used, along with the billion-rupee question of where Pāli came from, that is, the perennial puzzle of the ‘home’ of Pāli. In his *Pāli Literature and Language*, first published in German in 1916, pioneering Indologist Wilhelm Geiger wrote that ‘a consensus of opinion regarding the home of the dialect on which Pāli is based has ... not been achieved’.²⁸ According to the fifth-century master Ācariya Buddhaghosa, who was a partisan of the Mahāvihāra tradition, Pāli is Māgadhī, the language of Magadha (*māgadha-nirutti*, *māgadhika-bhāsā*, etc.) and is the root or foundation of all languages (*mūla-bhāsā*).

Modern scholarship has paid little heed to this and has embarked on a quest for the home of Pāli. By the time Maurice Winternitz (1863–1931) compiled his classic *History of Indian Literature*, a motley medley of theories and hypotheses about the origins of Pāli was already in circulation, and he gives a good summary of the diversity opinions.²⁹ N.L. Westergaard and E. Kuhn considered Pāli to be the dialect of Ujjain (ancient Ujjayanī), relating it to Aśoka’s Girnar inscription and to the legend that Asoka’s son Mahinda travelled from Ujjain to establish the Śāsanā in Ceylon.³⁰ R.O. Franke and Sten Konow also related Pāli to Ujjain and the Vindhya region, the latter seeing a close relationship between Pāli and Paiśācī, which he held to come from the Ujjain region. Others like H. Oldenberg related Pāli to the Kāliṅga country.³¹ Geiger himself agreed with E. Windisch in falling ‘back on the old tradition’—that Pāli was a kind of Māgadhī, an Ardhāmāgadhī. A hundred years have passed, and the situation has not much changed, except that the theory of western origins might be said to prevail in a highly contested speculative landscape. This leaves Ujjain and the Vindhyas as possibilities.

More recently, Bhikkhu Bodhi writes on Pāli and Māgadhī,³²

The Theravāda tradition identifies Pāli with Māgadhī, the language of the state of Magadha, where the Buddha often stayed. Several of the Buddha’s favorite resorts were located in Magadha, among them the Bamboo Grove near Rājagaha, mentioned in the suttas as the scene of many discourses. As the language of a powerful and influential kingdom, Māgadhī may well have spread to other states in northeast India and become a prestigious language distinguishing those who used it as persons of culture, somewhat in the way English is used by the educated elite today even in the countries of South Asia. However, while the Buddha himself may have spoken in Māgadhī when teaching in Magadha—and perhaps in other dialects when teaching in

other states, such as Kosala—various features of Pāli indicate that it cannot be identified with Māgadhī as we know it from the earliest sources available to us, the edicts of King Aśoka.

No further inscriptions in Pāli have come to light and the only (relatively) recent evidence immediately relevant to Pāli is from Nepal. This is von Hinüber's edition and study of four folios from a palm-leaf manuscript of the *Vinaya Cullavagga* written in about the ninth century that comes from Kathmandu in Nepal. This is not a new discovery, having already been brought to public attention by Cecil Bendall (1856–1906) at the 12th International Congress of Orientalists held at Rome in October 1899, and described as 'un MS. Pāli, le premier qu'on ait trouvé dans l'Inde proprement dite' [A Pāli manuscript, the first which has been found in India properly speaking].³³ The situation has not changed—no further Pāli manuscripts have been found in India itself, and no Pāli manuscripts anywhere near as old as the Kathmandu manuscript have been found anywhere. Most Pāli manuscripts are from Sri Lanka or Southeast Asia, and they date to the nineteenth century, with others going back to the eighteenth and then some, much fewer in number, to earlier centuries, but not earlier than the fourteenth. About one thousand years after the inscriptions were indited, the region of production of Pāli manuscripts corresponds to that of the Pāli epigraphic zone. In terms of age of original documents, Pāli manuscripts have been eclipsed by the Gāndhārī manuscripts that have come to light over the last decades, some of which date to the first century CE and others perhaps even earlier. The production of Gāndhārī manuscripts seems to have stopped by the fourth century CE. The considerable difference in age between the two sets of manuscripts does not deflect from the value of the Pāli manuscripts, but it does introduce a radically new perspective to Buddhist manuscript studies.

One important result of von Hinüber's analysis that deserves emphasis and serious consideration is his finding that 'any hints of this [Kathmandu] manuscript having been copied from an original in Sinhalese script ... seem to be completely lacking'. It appears that the manuscript was copied from an earlier exemplar in a Gupta alphabet: that is, the original could not have come from Ceylon directly, and could indicate 'an established though perhaps very weak Mahāvihāra tradition in North India'. The material available—only four folios—'is by far too fragmentary to go beyond speculations ... and to reach the safe harbour of established facts'.³⁴

In brief, there is no Pāli zone in India and we cannot securely anchor the geographical origins of the Pāli tradition to any South Asian site. If Ujjain and the Vindhya are candidates, they are only that—possible candidates, and nothing beyond that. The areas in question is rich in Mauryan, that is Aśokan, relics, at Sanchi and Vidisha, and, quite possibly at Ujjain itself. The presence of Buddhist stūpas and Mauryan artefacts at Ujjain is not well publicized and excavations have been minimal. Several large stūpas in the vicinity of Ujjain have been described as Mauryan, presumably because of their size and shape and the size and composition of their bricks. About three miles north of the modern city of Ujjain at Undas lie two stūpas. One is a monumental mound known as Vaisya Tekri; beside it is a lesser mound known as Kumbhar Tekri. Both await excavation.³⁵ The stūpa at Shodanga beside the ancient city rampart alongside the River Shipra has yielded a pillar capital and a statue of an elephant that may be Mauryan, along with paving slabs inscribed with donors' names in post-Aśokan Brāhmī. These impressive artefacts are on display at the Vikram Kirti Mandir in the grounds of the Vikram University. The slabs were donated by Bhikhu Pusarakhita (Slab 1), Dharaka (Slab 2), and Nāgasena (Slab 3).³⁶ Another inscribed object, much later, from Shodanga is a conical terracotta seal that bears the *ye dhammā* formula.³⁷ Along the old Southern Routes (Dakṣiṇapatha), south of Vidisha and Sanchi, past the World Heritage rock shelter complex of Bhimbetka, along the fringes of the central Indian plateau in the foothills of the Vindhya lies a large Buddhist site known today as Panguraria (Dist. Sehore). Panguraria enjoys a splendid view of the broad Narmada plain; here two Aśokan inscriptions are written on the walls of a rock shelter, near which are two large stūpas. At one of these was found a monumental stone parasol donated by nuns. Behind, a forest of small stone stūpas and enclosures straggle through the underbrush far up the hill.³⁸

If Pāli cannot be securely placed on the map, there are two other Buddhist scriptural languages that can be. These are Gāndhārī Prakrit and Sāṃmatīya Prakrit. The new information from the study of the Gāndhārī Prakrit finds is sufficiently dramatic that I have referred to a 'Gāndhārī revolution' that, fueled by new manuscript discoveries, has transformed the field of Buddhist studies. Mainly from the northwestern subcontinent, and written in Gāndhārī Prakrit in the Kharoṣṭhī script, the manuscripts have inspired fresh insights into the textual, social, and ideological evolution of Buddhism. In contrast to the disembodied Pāli, the Gāndhārī texts can be securely placed in time and space: the very late centuries BCE and the early centuries CE, in 'greater Gandhāra', that

is, areas of present-day Afghanistan and Pakistan. These manuscripts are the oldest Buddhist manuscripts in existence, and indeed by far the oldest Indian manuscripts of any type.³⁹

The result of the Gāndhārī revolution is that the old models of the academic study of ‘early Buddhism’ have been overturned. They are no longer viable: the field of early Buddhism can no longer be restricted to Pāli but must be expanded to take into account Gāndhārī and other early Prakrits. Our venerable tools like The Pali Text Society’s *Pali–English Dictionary* (1921–1925) and the *Critical Pāli Dictionary* (1924–2011) were conceived and produced long before the Gāndhārī manuscripts became available. Pāli studies can no longer be a two-track affair of ‘Pāli versus Sanskrit’. I do not mean that it should now be treated as a three-track course, ‘Pāli–Gāndhārī–Sanskrit’, or even four, ‘Pāli–Gāndhārī–Bhaikṣukī/Saindhavī–Sanskrit’ but that the field has opened up and we need to recognize Pāli as one convoy on the Grand Trunk Road of Middle Indic languages—that the development of Buddhist scriptures involved a network of Middle Indic recitations interacting with grammatical and linguistic norms as well as with Sanskrit’s rise to linguistic predominance and its progressive pervasion of the intellectual sphere. Current and future Pāli studies, whether in Southeast Asia, Sri Lanka, Hong Kong, the UK, or anywhere else, need to reinvent themselves in a new frame. This is the greater context of Buddhist Prakrits.

In addition to Gāndhārī, we now have firm evidence of yet another Buddhist canonical Prakrit, that which was favoured by the Vātsīpurīya and Sāṃmatīya schools.⁴⁰ Here the texts so far accessible are few: the ‘Patna *Dhammapada*’ and the *Mañicūḍa-jātaka* by the great poet Sarvarakṣita, plus a few others written in the Bhaikṣukī or Saindhavī script.⁴¹ Here is a ‘new’ Buddhist language in a ‘new’ script. This language too may, possibly, be located in time and space, through a small number of Bhaikṣukī citation inscriptions from northern India, in the states of Bihar and Bengal. The painstaking investigations of Dragomir Dimitrov, however, suggest that the script that al-Biruni described as *Bhaikṣukī* in the early eleventh century should be properly identified as *Saindhavī*, that is, it belonged to ancient territory of Sindh in the lower Indus valley. Dimitrov identifies the language as well as Saindhavī Prakrit.

There are, however, no Prakrit/Saindhavī inscriptions in Sindh, or anywhere else in western India: could the northeast Indian inscriptions represent a ‘Saindhavī zone’ comparable to the Pāli zone of Southeast

Asia? The circumstances in western India were, however, very different from those of Southeast Asia. It seems that the Saindhavī *saṃghas* had to abandon their centres and leave Sindh after the Arab conquest in CE 712, and that some time after that they may have settled in northeast India. Very few inscriptions are known from the lower Indus valley and not much is clear about this period. Inscribed clay tablets retrieved from the great stūpa at Mirpurkhas are dated to the seventh to eight centuries; they give the *ye dharmā* stanza in Sanskrit in the Siddhamātrkā script.⁴² But such tablets are made with moulds; moulds are small and easily portable, and they could have been brought from almost anywhere and need not pertain to the local script. It seems that at present there are more questions than answers.

To return to Pāli: in relation to the received history of Theravāda, we find that this Indo-Aryan Prakrit that we call Pāli is not attested in the inscriptions of South Asia proper but is best attested in non-Indo-Aryan language regions of Southeast Asia. It is impossible to say whether Pāli had a centre, a heartland, and if so, where this was—or to determine when, how, and through what channels it spread within the subcontinent and beyond. The Pāli that we know today seems to have been redacted in central or western India, and then further processed in Sri Lanka and Southeast Asia. From the early period, redactors and reciters (*bhānakas*) were responsible for its oral preservation and oral transmission. Transmitted without letters or written manuscripts, carried in the memory of expert reciters, it could travel over a wide area and ‘settle’ as a scriptural language wherever there were compatible support systems.⁴³ According to Lankan histories, the first written Pāli manuscripts were produced in Sri Lanka in the first century BCE. None of these survive; the oldest surviving written Pāli is recorded as ritual texts on gold foils and stone bars in Southeast Asia from the middle of the first millennium CE. The inscribed objects of the Pāli zone are the earliest evidence there is of written Pāli.⁴⁴

What was the function of the Pāli epigraphs that do survive? Written Pāli was used for both empowerment and display. Empowerment means the installation of the word of the Buddha (*buddhavacana*) to empower, consecrate, or bless, a practice that for centuries was widespread among Buddhists across Asia, and continues to be practised, especially in Himalayan and Tibetan Buddhism. One of the most frequent empowering texts was, and is, conditioned arising (*paṭiccasamuppāda*), not only in Southeast but also in South Asia. Often the inscribed texts were luxury

editions, inscribed on gold.⁴⁵ As empowerments, Pāli texts functioned both ‘invisibly’ and ‘visibly’—*invisibly* when inscribed on slabs or tablets and installed within stūpas and *visibly* when inscribed in the open, to be seen. Visibility was part of a broader function of display, in which Pāli was inscribed on open and accessible objects such as pillars or rock surfaces. The visible display of texts is more common in the Southeast Asian Pāli zone than elsewhere, with the exception of the display versions of certain *dhāraṇīs* as recommended in the Indian texts themselves and widely practiced in the East Asian Sinosphere. These practices and functions overlap, and might be described as the warp and woof of early Buddhist citation inscriptions. As regards Southeast Asia, we can conclude that the Pyu and Dvāravatī societies shared in certain of the ritual practices of a wide Buddhistic world.

Buddhist scriptures evolved through complex language environments. Much is inaccessible: the long centuries of orality have evaporated with the mists of time, and untold numbers of written records have succumbed to impermanence. In the attempt to reconstruct what happened, it does not seem practicable to pit one language, one tradition, or one set of scriptures against the others as ‘older’, ‘more authentic’, or ‘more valuable’. It is more sensible to treat the different traditions as of equal value, as each having contributed to the preservation and dissemination of the Dharma. And, above all, to try to find out what they say, how they say it, and in what contexts. They are all ‘messages by the roadside’. Hopefully this approach will yield a balanced picture and will produce knowledge and new perspectives rather than to the recycling of a priori conclusions.

Notes

- 1 For example, we know almost nothing about the canons or intellectual productions of the schools that inhabited western India's rock-cut monasteries like those of the Junnar valley.
- 2 It might also be called a 'sphere', but I feel that 'Pālisphere' implies something bigger and more complex: the area(s) where Pāli has been used historically in ritual, liturgy and as a literary vehicle.
- 3 For Suvarnabhūmi, see Peter Skilling, 'Many Lands of Gold', in *Suvarnabhumi, the Golden Land: The new finding for Suvarnabhumi Terra Incognita*, edited by Bunchar Phongpanich and Somchet Thinapong, Bangkok: GISTDA (Geo-Informatics and Space Technology Development Agency) and BIA (Buddhadasa Indapanno Archives), 2019, pp. 191–217 along with the other essays in the collection.
- 4 What is 'mainland Southeast Asia'? For one answer, see Paul Sidwell and Mathias Jenny, eds., *The Languages and Linguistics of Mainland Southeast Asia: A Comprehensive Guide* (The World of Linguistics, Vol. 8), Berlin & Boston, De Gruyter Mouton, 2021 (hereafter LLMSA), pp. 1 ff. See also John N. Miksic and Geok Yian Goh, *Ancient Southeast Asia* (Routledge World Archaeology), London & New York: Routledge, pp. 1–6. For an engaging account of a leading archaeologist's lifelong exploration of the region's past, see Charles Higham, *Digging Deep: A Journey into Southeast Asia's Past*, Bangkok: River Books, 2022 (see also Higham's online lecture 'Digging Deep: A Journey into Southeast Asia's Past', Siam Society, 9 December 2021).
- 5 The language map of South and Southeast Asia is a spectrum and a jigsaw puzzle of languages from different language families. Popular or national presentations of broad-brush 'natural' or 'unitary' language zones are over-simplifications and very much open to question.
- 6 For Dvāravatī see *Defining Dvāravatī: Essays from the U Thong International Workshop 2017*, edited by Anna Bennett and Hunter Watson, Chiang Mai: Silkworm Books, 2019. In general see *Before Siam: Essays in Art and Archaeology*, edited by Nicolas Revire and Stephen A. Murphy, Bangkok: River Books/The Siam Society, 2014.
- 7 For Pyu epigraphy, language, and culture, see Marc Miyake, 'The Prehistory of Pyu, Keynote Talk', SEALS 2021; Arlo Griffiths, Bob Hudson, Marc Miyake, Julian K. Wheatley, 'Studies in Pyu Epigraphy, I: State of the Field, Edition and Analysis of the Kan Wet Khaung Mound Inscription, and Inventory of the Corpus', *Bulletin de l'École française d'Extrême-Orient*, 103 (2017), pp. 43–205.
- 8 For Tibeto-Burman languages, see George van Driem, *Languages of the Himalayas: An Ethnolinguistic Handbook of the Greater Himalayan Region*, 2 vols., Brill, 2001; Thomas Owen-Smith and Nathan W. Hill (ed.), *Trans-Himalayan Linguistics: Historical and Descriptive Linguistics of the Himalayan Area* (Trends in Linguistics. Studies and Monographs [TiLSM] Volume 266), Berlin: De Gruyter, 2014.
- 9 In general see LLMSA Chap. 35, MSEA Epigraphy, pp. 855–877; LLMSA Chap. 36, Writing Systems of MSEA, pp. 879–906.
- 10 The classification and affiliation of language families and groups undergo regular revisions and remain contentious insofar as new insights tend to run against the grain of myopic national-historical narratives that seek to conflate the 'national' with the 'natural'.
- 11 For Austroasiatic languages in India, see Tony Joseph, *Early Indians: The Story of Our Ancestors and Where We Came From*, New Delhi: Juggernaut Books, 2018, pp. 152–159.
- 12 See Joseph, *Early Indians*, pp. 154–157.
- 13 See Peter Skilling, 'The Advent of Theravāda Buddhism to Mainland South-east Asia', *Journal of the International Association of Buddhist Studies* 20/1 (1997), pp. 93–107.
- 14 An exception is the brief treatment at LLMSA § 35.7, pp. 871–872. See Arlo Griffiths, in 'Early Indic Inscriptions of Southeast Asia', in *Lost Kingdoms: Hindu-Buddhist Sculpture of Southeast Asia*, edited by John Guy, New York: The Metropolitan Museum of Art, 2014, pp. 53–57 (endnotes, p. 276); P. Skilling, 'Precious Deposits: Buddhism Seen through Inscriptions in Early Southeast Asia', in idem., pp. 58–62 (endnotes, pp. 276–277).

- 15 Peter Skilling, 'An Untraced Buddhist Verse Inscription from (Pen)insular Southeast Asia', in *Buddhist Dynamics in Premodern and Early Modern Southeast Asia*, edited by D. Christian Lammerts, Singapore: Institute of Southeast Asian Studies, 2015, pp. 18–79. For a later and even stunning example of trans-Asian intertextuality exemplified by a Cambodian inscription of one single verse by the great Buddhist poet Mātṛcēta, see idem., 'Namo Buddhāya Gurave (K. 888): Circulation of a Liturgical Formula across Asia', *Journal of the Siam Society* vol. 106 (2018), pp. 109–128. For Mahāyāna and dhāraṇī inscriptions in insular Southeast Asia, see the important contributions of Arlo Griffiths.
- 16 See, for example, Peter Skilling, 'Sāgaramati-paripṛcchā Inscriptions from Kedah, Malaysia', in *Reading Slowly, A Festschrift for Jens E. Braarvig*, edited by Lutz Edzard, Jens W. Borgland, and Ute Hüsken, Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz Verlag, 2018, pp. 433–460. Dhāraṇīs are often inscribed not in the local script but in the north Indian Siddhamātrkā. For 'esoteric Buddhism' in general, see the essays in Andrea Acri, ed., *Esoteric Buddhism in Mediaeval Maritime Asia: Networks of Masters, Texts, Icons* (Nalanda-Sriwijaya series, 27), Singapore: ISEAS–Yusuf Ishak Institute, 2016.
- 17 On the whole, these findings agree with those of Prapod Assavavirulhakarn: see his *The Ascendancy of Theravāda Buddhism in Southeast Asia*, Chiang Mai: Silkworm Books, 2010.
- 18 'Early' is a relative term. There are no early Pāli inscriptions anywhere; those under mention belong to the 'middle' period of about the fifth to the tenth century CE.
- 19 For Vaitulya, Vaidalya, and Vaipulya, see P. Skilling, 'Vaidalya, Mahāyāna, and Bodhisatva in India: An essay towards historical understanding', in *The Bodhisatva Ideal: Essays on the Emergence of the Mahāyāna*, edited by Bhikkhu Nyanatusita, Kandy: Buddhist Publication Society, 2013, pp. 69–162; idem., *Questioning the Buddha: A Selection of Twenty-Five Sutras*, Somerville: Wisdom Books, 2021, pp. 47–65.
- 20 Lanka is rich in early donative inscriptions in Sinhala Prakrit; these pertain to contemporaneous language use and not to the canonical usages of Buddhist schools. See Nandasena Mudiyanse, 'A Short History of the Sinhala Language', in *Buddhist and Indian Studies in Honour of Professor Sodo Mori*. Hamamatsu: Kokusai Bukkyoto Kyokai (International Buddhist Association), pp. 547–554. This was an age when in South Asia all donative epigraphs were in Prakrit or, in the Dravidian lands, in Tamil.
- 21 Note that in the early nineteenth century European observers described *all* Prakrit inscriptions as 'Pāli' or 'Arrian Pāli', and so on. These early usages stem from confusions current in early European scholarship. Some modern authorities have used the term 'continental Pāli' for, for example, the Devnimori and Ratnagiri *pratītyasamutpāda* inscriptions. I leave aside here the rich epigraphic records of one other major South Asian language group, Dravidian, with its early and extensive corpus of Tamil inscriptions.
- 22 See the online *Early Inscriptions of Andhradeśa*: hisoma.hum-num-fr.
- 23 A recent study is Andrew Ollett, *Language of the Snakes: Prakrit, Sanskrit, and the Language Order of Premodern India*, Berkeley: University of California Press, 2017.
- 24 Oskar von Hinüber and Peter Skilling, 'Two Buddhist Inscriptions from Deorkothar (Dist. Rewa, Madhya Pradesh)', *Annual Report of the International Research Institute for Advanced Buddhology at Soka University for the Academic Year 2012*, Vol. XVI, Tokyo: The International Research Institute for Advanced Buddhology, Soka University, 2013, pp. 13–36, pls. 4–11.
- 25 *Phanigiri: Interpreting an Ancient Buddhist Site in Telangana*, edited by Naman Ahuja, Marg Publications, Mumbai/Department of Heritage Telangana, 2020.
- 26 Maiko Nakanishi and Oskar von Hinüber, *Kanaganahalli Inscriptions, Supplement to Annual Report of The International Research Institute for Advanced Buddhology for the Academic Year 2013*, Vol. XVII, Tokyo: The International Research Institute for Advanced Buddhology, 2014; Monika Zin, *The Kanaganahalli Stūpa: An Analysis of the 60 Massive Slabs Covering the Dome*, New Delhi: Aryan Books International, 2018.
- 27 Oskar von Hinüber, 'Epigraphical Varieties of Continental Pāli', [1985] repr. in Oskar von Hinüber, *Kleine Schriften*, edited by Harry Falk and Walter Slaje, Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz Verlag, 2009, Vol. I, pp. 489–504.

- 28 I quote from the revised English translation: Wilhelm Geiger, *Pāli Literature and Language*, translated by Batakrishna Ghosh, 1942 (second edition, 1968, original German edition 1916), p. 4.
- 29 Winternitz, *History of Indian Literature*, Vol. II, Appendix II, Third edition, New Delhi, 1991, pp. 601–605.
- 30 More recently, see Collette Caillat, ‘Some idiosyncracies of language and style in Asoka’s Rock Edicts at Girnar’, *Selected Papers*, Bristol: The Pāli Text Society, 2011, No. 19; Richard Gombrich, ‘Introduction: What is Pāli?’ in W. Geiger, *A Pāli Grammar*, revised and edited by K.R. Norman, Oxford, The Pali Text Society, 1994, pp. xxiii–xxix, and idem., *Buddhism and Pāli*, Oxford: Mud Pie Books, 2018; Thomas Oberlies, *Pāli: A Grammar of the Language of the Theravāda Tipitaka*, [2001] Delhi: Munshiram Manoharlal Publishers Pvt. Ltd., 2012, esp. pp. 1–16. In this age of ‘search’ mentality it is fruitless to attempt any sort of comprehensive bibliography of these topics. One can only recommend readers consult the works written or edited by K.R. Norman, Richard Gombrich, Heinz Bechert, O. von Hinüber, and the other stalwarts of Pāli studies. Much of the literature is in German, modern philology’s canonical language.
- 31 Kāliṅga does indeed possess Asokan inscriptions and artefacts and Buddhism had a continual presence there up to the mediaeval period and perhaps later.
- 32 Bhikkhu Bodhi, *Reading the Buddha’s Discourses in Pāli: A Practical Guide to the Language of the Ancient Buddhist Canon*, Somerville, Mass.: Wisdom Publications, 2020, p. 1.
- 33 Oskar von Hinüber, *The Oldest Pali Manuscript: Four Folios of the Vinaya-Pitaka from the National Archives, Kathmandu (Untersuchungen Zur Sprachgeschichte Und Handschriftenkunde Des Pali II)*, 1991, p. 5.
- 34 Ibid., pp. 25–26.
- 35 See Peter Skilling, ‘Stūpas, Aśoka, and Buddhist nuns: Early Buddhism in Ujjain and Malwa’, *Bulletin of the Asia Institute*, New Series, Vol. 25 (2011 [2015]), pp. 164–165 (whole article, pp. 157–173).
- 36 Skilling, ‘Stūpas, Aśoka, and Buddhist nuns’, pp. 160–162.
- 37 Ibid., pp. 162–164.
- 38 Ibid., pp. 167–169. For the central Indian sites mentioned here see R.C. Agrawal’s well illustrated *Conservation of Buddhist Monuments in Central India*, Delhi: Sharada Publishing House, 2015.
- 39 For a recent summary of the finds, see Richard Salomon, *The Buddhist Literature of Ancient Gandhāra: An Introduction with Selected Translations* (Classics of Indian Buddhism), Somerville, Mass.: Wisdom Publications, 2018.
- 40 For these schools, see P. Skilling, ‘Rehabilitating the *Pudgalavādins*: Monastic culture of the Vātsīputrīya-Sāṃmitīya School’, *Journal of Buddhist Studies* XIII (2016) (Centre for Buddhist Studies, Sri Lanka and The Buddha-Dharma Centre of Hong Kong), pp. 1–53; idem., ‘The Vātsīputrīya/Sāṃmitīya: Buddhist Personalism as a Mainstream School of Thought’, in *Routledge Handbook of Indian Buddhist Philosophy*, edited by Sara McClintock, Pierre-Julien Harter, and William Edelglass, Routledge, UK, 2022.
- 41 For details see Dragomir Dimitrov, *The Buddhist Indus Script and Scriptures: On the so-called Bhaiṣṣukī or Saindhavī Script of the Sāṃmitīyas and their Canon*, Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz Verlag, 2020.
- 42 Sabyasachi Mukherjee, ‘The Reconstruction of a Buddhist Stupa at Mirpurkas’, in *Sindh: Past Glory. Present Nostalgia*, edited by Pratapaditya Pal, Mumbai: Marg Publications, 2008, pp. 62–73 and esp. pl. 3.
- 43 This is true of any of the several canonical languages.
- 44 Early Chinese reports on Funan refer to palm-leaf manuscripts written in Indic scripts, but none whatsoever survive.
- 45 Some of the inscriptions may have funerary connections.

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CONTENTS

‘Visions of the Buddha’: A Critical Reply Bhikkhu ANĀLAYO	1
Epigraphic Pāli as a Southeast Asian Geographic Zone Peter SKILLING (Rudra RUJIRATHAT)	37
Buddhist Faith and Chinese Manuscript Culture: A Fruitful Encounter Pietro DE LAURENTIS	53
A Fragment of <i>Samghaṭasūtra</i> Interpolated in the Manuscript of the <i>Bodhicaryavatārapañikā</i> (ZX0617–ZB20) Junqi WANG, Lan FANG, Juan LIAO, Meifang Zhang	87
Clearing the Path Continues: Notes on Ñāṇavīra Thera's 'Notes of Dhamma' Bhikkhu ANĀLAYO	97
<i>Sarabhañña</i> , an Esthetic Delivery of Dhamma: Origins and Structure Bhikkhu MIHITA	119
Impact of Buddhist Values on Chinese Social Life in Contemporary China: Criticism and Counter-criticism of Yinshun’s Humanistic Buddhism in Mainland China WEI SHAN	165
Exposition on the Elements (<i>Dhātunirdeśa</i>) Chapter I of <i>Abhidharmakośabhāṣya</i> – Part III KL DHAMMAJOTI	197

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